

SEQUESTERED LEARNING AS A PRELUDE TO COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES AND ITS IMPACT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN GENERAL BIOLOGY

Jesson B. Lungay
Vera A. Villocido, MA

*Holy Name University, Janssen Heights, J. A. Clarin Street Dampas District 6300
Tagbilaran City, Bohol, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the impact of sequestered learning, which uses headsets to create a distraction-free environment, on the academic performance of Grade 11 STEM students in General Biology at Calape National High School. Employing a quasi-experimental design, the research involved 60 students divided into two groups: an experimental group that experienced sequestered learning and a control group that received traditional instruction. Performance was assessed through pretests and posttests, with results analyzed using t-tests. The study found that students in the experimental group, who received instruction via headsets, demonstrated significantly improved performance compared to those in the control group. This improvement aligns with Cognitive Load Theory, which emphasizes the reduction of cognitive overload to enhance learning. Additionally, the study supports the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), highlighting how technology integration can positively impact student engagement and performance. The findings are further supported by Selective Attention Theory, which underscores the benefits of focused learning environments in filtering out distractions. The results suggest incorporating technology such as headsets in educational settings can effectively enhance instructional delivery and student outcomes. By reducing external distractions and improving focus, sequestered learning creates a more conducive environment for understanding and retaining instructional content. This research provides valuable insights into optimizing teaching strategies and leveraging technology to foster academic success and engagement in STEM education.

Keywords: *Biology, Sequestered Learning, Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Education is fundamental in unlocking an individual's full potential, equipping them with essential knowledge, skills, and attitudes to lead productive and fulfilling lives. Beyond their role in delivering knowledge, teachers are pivotal in inspiring, mentoring, and guiding students. Effective teaching encompasses understanding diverse learners, creating a positive learning environment, and adapting to students' evolving needs.

Despite the Philippine government's efforts to improve education quality, indicators reveal a persistent education crisis (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024). While educators strive to enhance teaching-learning processes, instructional designers continue to seek optimal methods for student academic performance (Molla, 2018). Diverse and interactive teaching strategies and educational technology are crucial for maintaining student engagement and attention (Das & Barman, 2024).

In biology classrooms, students often struggle with performance during interactive, collaborative activities due to missing key instructions, exacerbated by environmental noise. This study introduces a sequestered learning approach using headsets to provide focused, uninterrupted instruction as a preparatory phase before collaborative activities. This method aims to ensure that students fully understand instructions, thus enhancing their participation and performance in collaborative tasks.

Sequestered learning seeks to create a concentrated learning environment by isolating students from external distractions and using headsets. This approach improves students' comprehension and retention of instructional content, ultimately supporting better engagement and academic success. Technology, such as noise-cancelling headphones, has been shown to impact learning outcomes by reducing distractions and enhancing focus positively (Yu et al., 2016; Chow et al., 2018). Studies highlight the benefits of such technology in various educational settings, including improved performance, concentration, and reduced anxiety (Molesworth et al., 2013; Kulawiak, 2021).

The Cognitive Load Theory by John Sweller (1998) underpins this study, emphasizing that minimizing cognitive overload can enhance learning outcomes. Noise contributes to cognitive overload, impairing effective learning. Sequestered learning, with headsets aiding in instruction delivery, aligns with this theory by reducing extraneous cognitive load and supporting effective communication between students and teachers.

Additionally, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) by Venkatesh et al. (2003) provides a framework for understanding technology adoption in education. This theory helps assess how headsets, as part of sequestered learning, influence students' acceptance and usage of technology, impacting their engagement and performance.

Donald Broadbent's Selective Attention Theory further supports the use of headsets in sequestered learning by emphasizing the need to focus on relevant information and filtering out distractions. Headsets can help students concentrate better, enhancing comprehension and retention of instructional content.

John Dewey's educational philosophy advocates for active engagement and experiential learning. Sequestered learning, using headsets to minimize external distractions, supports this philosophy by allowing students to immerse themselves in instructional content without interruptions.

The integration of technology, particularly headsets, has transformed education, making it possible to create immersive, engaging learning environments. This study investigates the impact of sequestered learning using headsets on the academic performance of Grade 11 STEM students at Calape National High School. It seeks to contribute to improving classroom instruction and delivery, ensuring that students receive essential instructions and have the background knowledge necessary for productive collaborative activities.

The findings from this research will provide insights into how technology-enhanced sequestered learning can foster a more inclusive and effective educational environment, ultimately supporting academic success and student engagement.

Research Questions

The study investigated the use of Sequestered Learning as a Prelude to Collaborative Activities and its impact on the academic performance in General Biology of the Grade 11 STEM Medical and Grade 11 STEM Engineering students at Calape National High School, Sta. Cruz, Calape, Bohol for the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the academic performance of the control group using the traditional method of delivering instruction and the experimental group using sequestered delivery of instruction in the:
 - 1.1. pretest; and
 - 1.2. posttest?
2. Is there a significant difference between the result of the pretest and posttest of the:
 - 2.1. control group; and
 - 2.2. experimental group?
3. Is there a significant difference between the performance of the control group and the experimental group:
 - 3.1. pretest; and
 - 3.2. posttest?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quasi-experimental design. Two Grade 11 STEM classes were selected. One class served as the experimental group with 30 students, where a sequestered learning delivery of instruction was integrated into the general biology subject. In contrast, the other class acted as a control group with 30 students and received traditional instruction without the sequestered learning delivery of instruction integration.

Research Environment

The study was conducted at Calape National High School in Barangay Sta. Cruz, Calape, Bohol, 38 kilometers from Tagbilaran City. The school, which offers junior high school (Grades 7-10) and senior high school strands (STEM, HUMSS, ABM, and TVL), is the largest public high school in the Calape District. With a student population of 1,603, it serves a diverse student body from various backgrounds and academic levels. The researcher, who teaches General Biology to Grade 11 STEM students, noted low academic performance and explored various teaching methods before proposing this research. The decision to use sequestered learning delivery of instruction was influenced by observed challenges in the teaching-learning process and the availability of technology, including headsets, at the school.

Research Participants

The study involved 60 Grade 11 STEM students from Calape National High School, selected for their alignment with the General Biology curriculum and similar academic performance. Two sections were chosen based on comparable student numbers, performance, and teacher assignments, with one section as the control group and the other as the experimental group.

Students and their guardians provided informed consent and assent, with confidentiality ensured. Students with irregular attendance or lacking consent were included in daily activities but excluded from pre-test and post-test analyses.

An enrichment class was offered post-study for the control group to cover the experimental group's strategies. The general biology teacher and the researcher implemented the study using a self-designed lesson plan, with oversight and support from the school's science coordinator.

Table 1. Distribution of Participants

Group	Number of Participants
11 STEM Engineering (control group)	30
11 STEM Medical (experimental group)	30
Total	60

Research Instrument

The researcher carefully prepared the pretest and posttest instruments. This was designed to determine the achievement of the respondents in General Biology both in the pretest and posttest. The preparation and validation of the test are as follows:

a. Planning the test. The test covered the topics of the third quarter period as reflected in the competencies found in the Department of Education curriculum guide.

b. Preparation of the Questionnaire. The researcher used a Table of Specifications to serve as a guide in making the questionnaire. Such was based on the competencies found in the Department of Education curriculum guide. It was then presented to other science teachers at other levels in Calape National High School for comments and suggestions.

c. Pilot-testing. The first trial run was given to the Grade 12 students of Calape National High School since they already had these lessons. The students were given an hour to finish the entire test.

d. Item Analysis. Thereafter, test papers were gathered and checked by the researcher. An item analysis was conducted following the formula on the index of difficulty and the discrimination index. Items were accepted if they fell on the acceptable difficulty and discrimination indices. Items were subjected to revision if they had an acceptable difficulty index but an unacceptable discrimination index. Items that do not fall into the accepted range will be rejected.

e. Test Reliability. Items accepted and used for pretest and posttest were determined using the formula on the index of difficulty and discrimination index.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first sought permission from the principal of Calape National High School to conduct the study and test a teacher-made test with Grade 12 students. Detailed lesson plans were then prepared for both the experimental and control groups. The experimental group utilized a sequestered learning approach with headsets, while the control group followed traditional instruction methods. Both sets of lesson plans complied with Department of Education guidelines. Before the intervention, both groups

were administered a pretest, with scores collected and recorded for analysis. During the study, the experimental group was taught using the sequestered learning method before engaging in collaborative activities, whereas the control group continued with traditional instruction. The same topics and problems were covered in both groups over four weeks, with four 60-minute weekly sessions. Following the intervention, a posttest was administered to assess the effectiveness of the instructional methods. The pretest and posttest results were analyzed using the t-test for correlated means, with data processed through SPSS software and Microsoft Excel.

Data Analysis

After the responses were gathered and tallied, the following statistical treatments were used in the analysis of data:

To identify the performance of the grade 11 STEM Engineering and 11 STEM Medical students using the sequestered learning and the traditional teaching-learning approach in the general biology science subject, the percentage was used:

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

The computed percentage was interpreted using the following grading scale:

Grading Scale	Description
36 and above	Advance
32 – 35	Proficient
28 – 31	Approaching Proficient
24 – 27	Developing
23 and below	Beginning

To identify the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the control and experimental group, the t-test for dependent samples was used. It was computed with the formula:

$$\frac{\sum D}{\frac{\sqrt{[N(\sum D^2) - (\sum D)^2]}}{(N - 1)}}$$

To determine the significant difference between the control and experimental groups of the pre-test and post-test, the t-test of independent samples was used. It was computed with the formula:

$$t = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)s_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 - 2} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right]}}$$

RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets data from pretest and post-test results to evaluate the impact of Sequestered Learning on the academic performance of Grade 11 STEM students in General Biology at Calape National High School. It is divided into three sections: First, it examines the academic outcomes of both the control group, which received traditional instruction, and the experimental group, which used Sequestered Learning with headsets. The second section compares the performance differences between Grade 11 STEM Engineering students who experienced Sequestered Learning and Grade 11 STEM Medical students taught using conventional methods. Finally, the chapter contrasts the pretest and post-test results for both groups to assess the effect of Sequestered Learning and traditional instruction on student performance in General Biology.

Academic Performance of the Grade 11 STEM students in General Biology

Table 2 illustrates the pre-test results of Grade 11 STEM Engineering and 11 STEM Medical students, categorized into control and experimental groups, within their General Biology class.

Table 2. Pre-test Result.

INDICATOR		Experimental Group		Control Group	
Category	Range	f	%	F	%
Advanced	36-40	0	0	0	0
Proficient	32-35	0	0	0	0
Approaching Proficiency	28-31	0	0	0	0
Developing	24-27	1	3.33	0	0
Beginning	23 and below	29	96.67	30	100.00
Total =		30	100.00	38	100.00

In both the experimental and control groups, no students reached the "Advanced" or "Proficient" levels, as indicated by the absence of scores in the 36-40 or 32-35 ranges, respectively. Neither group had students classified as "Approaching Proficiency," with scores falling in the 28-31 range. Only 1 student (3.33%) in the experimental group achieved the "Developing" category, while none in the control group did, highlighting a minimal level of proficiency in both groups. Most students were in the "Beginning" category, with 29 students (96.67%) in the experimental group and all 30 students (100%) in the control group scoring 23 or below. This indicates that most are at the beginning stages of proficiency and require significant support.

Table 2 reveals that both groups have similar, limited knowledge of the subject matter, suggesting a need for targeted interventions to improve proficiency.

Table 3 compares the posttest results for Grade 11 STEM Engineering and Medical students, contrasting the experimental group, which received Sequestered Learning with technology headsets, and the control group.

The table shows the distribution of students across five performance categories, providing insights into the effectiveness of the Sequestered Learning intervention in improving academic performance.

Table 3. Post-test Result.

INDICATOR		Experimental Group		Control Group	
Category	Range	f	%	f	%
Advanced	36-40	7	23.33	0	0.00
Proficient	32-35	2	6.67	0	0.00
Approaching Proficiency	28-31	6	20.00	2	6.67
Developing	24-27	3	10.00	2	6.67
Beginning	23 and below	12	40.00	26	86.67
Total =		30	100.00	30	100.00

The posttest results show a significant difference in scores between the experimental group, which received sequestered learning, and the control group. In the experimental group, 7 students (23.33%) achieved "Advanced" scores, 2 students (6.67%) were "Proficient," 6 students (20%) were "Developing," and 12 students (40%) were "Beginning." This indicates that the intervention notably improved student proficiency levels. In contrast, the control group had no students in the "Advanced" or "Proficient" categories, 2 students (6.67%) in "Approaching Proficiency," 2 students (6.67%) in "Developing," and 26 students (86.67%) in "Beginning."

The experimental group had 40% of students in the "Beginning" category, compared to 86.67% in the control group, suggesting that sequestered learning helped reduce the number of students at the lowest proficiency level. The experimental group also outperformed the control group in the "Advanced," "Proficient," and "Approaching Proficiency" categories, with 23.33%, 6.67%, and 20% of students in these categories, respectively, while the control group had no students in these levels.

Overall, the sequestered learning intervention positively influenced student performance, reducing the proportion of students in the lowest proficiency levels and improving higher proficiency levels. Further analysis is needed to explore factors contributing to these outcomes. Table 4 compares the pretest and posttest results for the control group, providing insights into performance changes without the sequestered learning intervention.

Table 4. Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Results of the Control Group.

	n	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Computed t-value	Two-tailed (df=36, $\alpha=0.05$)		Decision
					Critical t-value	p-value	
Pretest	30	9.72	4.76	-4.36	± 2.01	0.00	Reject H_0
Posttest	30	16.24	6.48				

The pretest mean score was 9.72 with a standard deviation (SD) of 4.76, and the computed t-value was -4.36. On the other hand, the posttest mean score for the control group was 16.24 with a standard deviation of 6.48. In a two-tailed t-test with 36 degrees of freedom and a significance level (α) of 0.05, the critical t-value was ± 2.01 . The p-value was calculated to be 0.00, leading to the decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0).

The pretest results for the control group indicated a significant difference from the expected mean, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Further investigation may be needed to determine the specific causes behind this change in scores such as the strategies employed by the teacher.

Table 5. Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Results Experimental Group.

	n	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Computed t-value	Two-tailed (df=35, $\alpha=0.05$)		Decision
					Critical t-value	p-value	
Pretest	30	10.20	4.84	-8.67	± 2.02	0.00	Reject H_0
Posttest	30	26.52	8.90				

Table 5 provides a comparative analysis of the pretest and posttest results for the experimental group that experienced Sequestered Learning integration. Initially, the group had a pretest average score of 10.20 with a standard deviation of 4.84. After the Sequestered Learning intervention, the average score increased to 26.52, with a higher standard deviation of 8.90.

The t-value of -8.67, compared to the critical t-value for a two-tailed significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) with 35 degrees of freedom, resulted in a p-value of 0.00. This indicates a significant difference between pretest and posttest scores, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that Sequestered Learning significantly improved academic performance. However, the increased standard deviation in posttest scores implies greater variability, which may warrant further investigation to understand the impact and contributing factors fully.

Table 6 compares the pretest performance between the control group, which did not use Sequestered Learning, and the experimental group, which did.

Table 6. Difference between the Control and Experimental Groups in the Pre-test Result.

Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Computed t-value	Two-tailed (df=70, $\alpha=0.05$)		Decision
					Critical t-value	p-value	
Control	30	9.80	4.69	-0.27	± 2.00	0.79	Accept H_0
Experimental	30	10.13	4.78				

The control group, comprised of 30 individuals, exhibits a mean pretest score of 9.80 with a standard deviation of 4.69. In contrast, the experimental group, consisting of 30 individuals integrated with Sequestered Learning, has a slightly higher mean pretest score of 10.13, accompanied by a standard deviation of 4.78. The computed t-value of -0.27 reflects the difference between these two groups. The two-tailed t-test with a significance level (α) of 0.05 and 70 degrees of freedom shows a critical t-value of approximately ± 2.00 . The p-value associated with the t-test is 0.79.

Based on the result, the computed t-value (-0.27) falls within the range of the critical t-value (-2.00, +2.00). Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference between the control group that is not integrated with Sequestered Learning and the experimental group that is integrated with Sequestered Learning in their pretest scores.

Since Sequestered Learning has not yet been integrated into the delivery of the lesson before the conduct of the pretest, it has still no significant impact on the pretest performance of these two groups. While the experimental group has a slightly lower mean score, the difference is not statistically significant. However, it is important to note that other factors or variables not considered in this analysis could influence the observed results.

Table 7. Difference between the Control and Experimental Groups (Posttest).

Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Computed t-value	Two-tailed (df=70, $\alpha=0.05$)		Decision
					Critical t-value	p-value	
Control	30	16.24	6.48	-5.02	± 2.00	0.00	Reject H_0
Experimental	30	26.52	8.90				

Table 7 presents a comparative analysis of post-test results for the Control group (30 participants without Sequestered Learning) and the Experimental group (30 participants with Sequestered Learning integration). The table includes statistical measures such as sample size, mean scores, standard deviation, computed t-value, critical t-value, and p-value for a two-tailed test with a significance level of 0.05 and 70 degrees of freedom.

The Experimental group achieved a higher mean post-test score of 26.52 compared to the Control group's mean of 16.24, indicating better performance in the Experimental group. The standard deviation for the Experimental group (8.90) is greater than that for the Control group (6.48), suggesting increased variability in the Experimental group's scores.

The computed t-value of -5.02 exceeds the critical t-value of ± 2.00 , and the p-value of 0.00 confirms a statistically significant difference between the groups. This indicates that Sequestered Learning had a substantial impact on improving post-test scores, with the Experimental group showing significant improvement compared to the Control group.

This finding is consistent with studies conducted in Nigeria and the Philippines, which have demonstrated that technology integration, including Sequestered Learning, significantly enhances academic performance in Biology. Notable research by Emike and Ezeudu (2014), Agina-Obu et al. (2018), Onyema and Ogbu (2020), and Al-Rahmi et al. (2019) highlights the positive effects of technology on student performance. Similar trends were observed in the Philippines by Manzo and Bautista (2015), Ebrada and Cabrera (2017), and Arreola (2020), reinforcing the positive impact of technology on academic achievement.

The study's findings can be examined through Connectivism and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). Connectivism, which emphasizes networked learning, may explain the shift in proficiency levels observed in the Experimental group. The UTAUT framework highlights the importance of factors such as perceived ease of use and performance expectancy, which may have contributed to the significant improvements in the Experimental group.

Overall, the integration of Sequestered Learning significantly improved academic performance, as evidenced by the higher mean post-test scores and the statistical significance of the results. These findings underscore the potential benefits of technology integration in enhancing educational outcomes.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The highlights of the findings of this study are the following:

1. The pretest results of Grade 11 STEM students revealed that both the experimental group with Sequestered Learning Integration and the control

group had similar distributions of students across proficiency levels, with the majority in the "Beginning" category. None of the students in either group reached the "Advanced", "Proficient" or "Approaching Proficiency" levels, and a small percentage were in the "Developing" category, indicating room for improvement.

The post-test results, however, showed a significant contrast. In the experimental group, there was a significant improvement in higher proficiency levels, while the control group had a minor increase in the "Proficient" category. The most notable change was in the "Beginning" category, with the experimental group showing fewer students in this category compared to the control group. Additionally, the experimental group had some students in the "Approaching Proficiency" and "Developing" categories, while the control group had none.

2. The pretest results showed that the control group exhibited a significant difference from the expected mean, rejecting the null hypothesis. Furthermore, the increase in their mean score from pretest to posttest suggested that other factors influenced their performance. In contrast, the experimental group had significantly different pretest and posttest scores, with a notable increase in mean scores after Sequestered learning integration. The change in mean scores in the posttest implied a positive effect on the experimental group's performance.
3. The pretest results revealed no statistically significant difference between the two groups, with the experimental group showing a slightly lower mean pretest score. This suggests that the sequestered had no significant impact on the initial performance of the groups. However, in the posttest, the experimental group had a higher mean score than the control group, and this difference was statistically significant. It appears that the sequestered integration result had a significant improvement in post-test scores in this study, and other variables may influence the observed results.

Conclusions

Sequestered learning with the headset integration has a significant impact on the academic performance of the students indicating that the strategy applied in the experimental group was an effective intervention. This suggests that the integration of Sequestered Learning with the use of a headset can be an alternative strategy for improving the academic performance of the students in General Biology.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn by the researchers, it is recommended that:

1. **Further, investigate the impact on Higher Proficiency Levels:** Since the study indicated that Sequestered Learning Integration primarily prevented

students from falling into the lowest proficiency levels but had limited effectiveness in pushing them into higher proficiency levels, further research should delve into the specific factors contributing to this effect. Understanding why the technology integration didn't result in significant gains for higher proficiency levels is crucial for improving its effectiveness.

2. **Assess Long-Term Effects:** The study focused on the short-term impact of Sequestered Learning Integration. It's essential to conduct longitudinal research to examine whether the positive effects observed in the post-test are sustained over a more extended period. This will help determine if the Sequestered Learning integration has lasting benefits for students' academic performance.
3. **Evaluate the Role of Teacher Training:** The study did not delve into the level of training and support provided to teachers for implementing Sequestered Learning. Further research should assess whether teacher training and competence in using Sequestered Learning influence its impact on student's academic performance.
4. **Explore Additional Variables:** To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of Sequestered Learning Integration, it is crucial to consider other variables that may be affecting students' academic performance, such as student engagement, access to technology resources, and socioeconomic factors. Future studies should incorporate these variables to provide a more nuanced perspective on the relationship between sequential learning integration and student outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Any ethical concerns that could have risen throughout the study were resolved by securing necessary permits. Also, the researcher personally handed the research tools to the schools, with the assistance of the administrators, which included the informed consent form and questionnaires. Before data collection began, all research terms and conditions were fully disclosed to maintain transparency. Despite receiving clearance from the school principals and administrators, the researcher obtained informed consent from participants by individually requesting them to participate and providing thorough information about the study, including potential risks and benefits, as well as privacy safeguards. Each participant was asked to review and sign the informed consent form, indicating their comprehension and willingness to be involved in the study. It was optional to provide the participants' names, which were coded to preserve their identity. To safeguard data, further confidentiality measures were put in place, such as limiting access to physical and electronic resources. The study closely followed data privacy and research ethics guidelines, and participants were made aware of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any moment without facing consequences.

Proposed Action Plan

Rationale

Indeed, General Biology serves as a fundamental pillar in numerous fields, its principles underpinning advancements across engineering, medicine, agriculture, and environmental science. Yet, the abstract nature of biological concepts can pose significant challenges for students, potentially hindering their understanding and engagement. Traditional teaching methods often rely heavily on lectures and theoretical explanations, which may not effectively capture students' interest or facilitate deep comprehension.

Sequestered learning, also known as isolated or secluded learning, involves creating focused environments that minimize distractions and maximize concentration on the learning material. While sequestered learning can indeed offer benefits such as improved focus and reduced distractions, it's essential to consider its application within the context of General Biology education.

Sequestered learning can enhance student understanding and performance in General Biology by promoting focused engagement with the material, it's essential to strike a balance with other instructional approaches to ensure a comprehensive learning experience. Integrating sequestered learning with active learning strategies, collaborative activities, and real-world applications can create a dynamic and enriching environment that caters to diverse learning preferences and optimizes student learning outcomes in General Biology.

General Biology plays a crucial role in the Philippine educational system and beyond, serving as the cornerstone of scientific literacy and innovation. By highlighting the significance of General Biology education, fostering research and development, advocating interdisciplinary collaboration, and promoting ethical and sustainable practices, the Philippines can harness the transformative power of biology to address pressing challenges and unlock opportunities for progress and prosperity in the 21st century.

Indeed, integrating sequestered learning into General Biology education can offer numerous advantages to enhance student learning outcomes. Overall, the integration of sequestered learning into General Biology education offers a dynamic and effective approach to promoting student engagement, comprehension, and success in the discipline. By harnessing the benefits of sequestered environments, educators can create enriching learning experiences that empower students to thrive in their biology studies and beyond.

Thus, by implementing this action plan, educators can create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that promotes active learning, enhances conceptual understanding, and facilitates the concrete-to-abstract transition for students studying General Biology subjects.

Matrix

AREA OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES	PERSONS INVOLVE	TIME FRAME	EXPECTED OUTCOMES
Information Dissemination	To notify the Schools Division Superintendent and the Education Specialist in Science of the Division about the proposed training and for support.	Meeting with the Schools Division Superintendent and the Education Specialist in Science in the Division	Schools Division Superintendent and the Education Specialist in Science in the Division	First-Second week of May	Schools Division Superintendent will issue a Memorandum inspiring teachers to partake in the training.
	To report to the school head/principal on the findings of the study and the suggestion of conducting a teachers' training	Attending school and district meetings to inform the teachers about the study	District Supervisor/Coordinating Principal, School Head/Principal	Third week of May	School Heads/Principal and Science teachers already acknowledged the results and findings of the study
Memorandum Dissemination	To encourage Science teachers and other teachers to partake in the training.	Meeting with School Heads/Principal	Coordinating Principal, School Head/Principal	The first week of June	Teachers are informed and confirmed to attend the training.
Confirmation of Teacher Participants	To determine the number of participants who will join the training	Giving of invitation and validation letter		Fourth week of June	

AREA OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES	PERSONS INVOLVE	TIME FRAME	EXPECTED OUTCOMES
Conduct a Training Workshop	To enrich teachers' knowledge using sequestered learning	Training workshop in teaching Science using sequestered learning	Schools' Science Coordinators, Science teachers, and other non-science major teachers who are interested	Third week of July	The teacher has a complete understanding and background on how to be sequestered learning in
Teaching Demonstration					

and Integration of Physical Manipulatives	To have a clear understanding of how to integrate sequestered learning		to join the training		their respective schools
Planning and preparing instructional materials to be used for the integration of sequestered learning	To execute suitably the integration of learning	Collate relevant data and information related to the lesson and seek assistance from co-teachers	Science coordinators, Science teachers	All-year-round	Teachers are now ready to implement the integration of sequestered learning.
Enrichment/ Remedial Program	To assist students who find difficulty in Science.	Create an online discussion forum for students to post their questions and discuss with peers.	Science teachers, students	All year round	Students find Science as a challenging yet interesting subject

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